

D4.1 - Tailored methods and impactful tools for boosting BeBOP circularity opportunities

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Acronyms and abbreviations

BFB	Bubbling Fluidized Bed
CA	Circularity Assessment
CE	Circular Economy
CEP	Circular Economy Principle
CTI	Circular Transition Indicators
CRM	Critical Row Materials
EN	European Norm
EoL	End-of-life
ESRS	European Sustainability Reporting Standards
GRI	Global Reporting Initiative standards
H4C	Hubs for Circularity
ISO	International Standardization Organization
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
MCI	Material Circularity Indicator
OENORM	Austrian Standards Organization
SA	Sustainability Assessment
SOEC	Solid Oxide Electrolysis Cells
SOFC	Solid Oxide Fuel Cells

Acronyms used to identify consortium members

ECODESIGN	ECODESIGN company GmbH
VTT	Technical Research Centre of Finland

Publishable executive summary

The aim of this report, "Deliverable 4.1: Tailored Methods and Impactful Tools for Boosting BeBOP Circularity Opportunities," is to provide tailored methods and actionable tools to identify, enhance and validate circularity opportunities within the BeBOP project, particularly focusing on the methanol synthesis value chain. The EU funded BeBOP project aims to develop an innovative biomass-to-methanol plant that could revolutionize the methanol industry. By integrating an electrolysis cell (SOEC), the project could double methanol productivity, achieve over 95% carbon efficiency, and recover high-value components from biomass residues. This could lower methanol production costs to below €250 per ton and prevent over 30 million tons of CO₂ emissions annually, creating new market opportunities.

The report begins by defining the Circular Economy (CE) principles, i.e., 1. narrowing, 2. slowing, 3. closing, and 4. regenerating resource flows, and distinguishing Circularity Assessments (CA) from the traditional Life Cycle Assessments (LCA), emphasizing how the Circular Assessments solution-oriented approach is able to optimise resource flows. The report's core provides a detailed overview of the objectives and strategy for a series of six workshops designed to identify the key factors able of improving the scaled-up BeBOP plant's circularity: i.e. the so-called BeBOP Circularity Workshops. It presents the challenges in applying existing circularity frameworks, which are often product-focused, to an industrial process in its design phase. Furthermore, the methodology involves linking specific BeBOP value chain segments to each different workshop, engaging relevant internal and external stakeholders, applying the four CE principles to define topics of interest, and formulating detailed discussion questions to identify effective circularity levers. The report uses the SOEC unit as an example to illustrate how these CE principles and discussion questions are applied in practice in the workshop concept. These methods support a multi-stakeholder dialogue, grounded in both qualitative and quantitative approaches, and are validated through dedicated workshops. The findings from these workshops are intended to inform strategies for sustainable circularity, which will be further detailed in a subsequent deliverable (D4.2 "Validated strategies for ensuring sustainable circularity plans").

1. Introduction

The primary rationale for producing Methanol from biomass and electricity (Bio/e-Methanol) is to substitute fossil fuels with a process based on renewables—specifically, regenerative materials (biomass) and renewable energy. Consequently, the Sustainability Assessment (SA) plays a core role in the BeBOP project and is addressed through two sets of methods: a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) (which will be explored during the implementation of both WP5, *Preliminary system analysis*, and WP6, *Final system analysis*) and a Circularity Assessment (CA) (which is currently investigated for the implementation of WP4, *Circularity of the BeBOP plant and its Hubs*). While the LCA is a quantitative and established method; the CA encompasses a range of methods and toolsets that need to be modified based on the outcomes and purposes that are intended to be addressed. Table 1 to follow outlines the key differences between these two assessment methods.

	Circularity Assessment (covered in WP4)	Life Cycle Assessment (covered in WP5 and WP6)
Methodology	Solution-oriented methodology to identify: a) Product design, and b) Business Model opportunities, that optimize the flow of resources.	Assessment-oriented methodology which aims to: a) Quantify the environmental impacts; b) Identify different hotspots; c) Compare various product systems.
Standardization	Wide range of approaches and tools, mostly related to end-user products.	Well established assessment method (e.g. ISO 14040/44), applicable to a wide range of sectors, product systems, processes.
Focus	Focuses on physical and regenerative flows and their optimization.	Standardized impact assessment covering a wide range of quantifiable impact categories.
Data Availability	Evolving generic KPIs related to circularity metrics with few sector-based adaptations (e.g., ISO 59020).	Detailed impact assessment methodology and extensive standardized and detailed databases for a wide range of industrial processes.

Table 1: Differences between Circularity Assessments and Life Cycle Assessments

2. Defining Circular Economy and Circularity Approaches

2.1. Definition of a Circular Economy

A Circular Economy is an economic system that uses a systemic approach to maintain a circular flow of resources by recovering, retaining or adding to their value, while contributing to sustainable development¹.

2.2. Circularity approaches

One of the most well-known infographics illustrating the basics of a Circular Economy is the "Butterfly Diagram" by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation. The centre of the diagram depicts the typical linear flow of resources for a generic product (Figure 1), beginning with material mining, followed by parts and product manufacturing, the use phase, and finally, the product's end-of-life (EoL), assumed to be a combination of energy recovery and landfilling. Ideally, this linear lifecycle should be extended by loops designed to keep resources within the economic system for as long as possible. These include strategies that extend the lifetime of components or entire products, such as cascading, maintenance, repair, and reuse which compose the "*inner loops*", as well as strategies that retain materials within the loop through recycling, i.e. the "*outer loops*".

On its left and right sides, respectively, the diagram differentiates between biological and technical cycles of resources. The biological cycle is composed of resources that are organic and renewable (e.g., food, wood, bioplastics), that should be safely returned to nature after use. Differently, the resources in the technical cycle (e.g., metals, plastics, electronics) are synthetic and engineered, therefore, they should ideally be returned to the industry sector as efficiently as possible implementing the 4R processes: Reuse, Repair, Remanufacture and Recycling.

This framework can be further simplified by considering how resource flows can be narrowed, slowed, closed, and regenerated². These four efforts to optimize resource flows are referred to as Circular Economy Principles (CEP). Figure 1 roughly correlates these four principles with the flows depicted in the Butterfly Diagram. The four CEPs are defined as follows:

- 1) **Narrowing** focuses on using less energy and materials per use. This principle primarily encompasses measures in the production phase related to energy and resource efficiency. However, it also includes measures like designing a product for multiple functions or increasing a product's use intensity through sharing (e.g., fleet management for professional tools), which ultimately decreases and therefore narrows overall resource demand.
- 2) **Slowing** pertains to the "*inner loops*" of the Butterfly Diagram, where the service life of products or components is extended through strategies such as maintenance, repair, reuse, remanufacturing, and cascade use. Optimally, these *inner loops* are encouraged

¹ See definition included in ISO 59004:2024

² Bocken et al., "Product Design and Business Model Strategies for a Circular Economy."

by product design that, for example, utilizes standardized components and facilitates disassembly and reassembly.

- 3) **Closing** refers to the recovery of resources at the material level. It encompasses approaches that use recycled inputs as well as those that provide recycled materials. From the perspective of the chemical industry, the principle of "*Industrial Symbiosis*" is particularly relevant, involving the strategic co-location and sharing of previously considered "waste streams" (mainly water, energy, and materials) among different industries.
- 4) **Regenerate** refers to the use of non-toxic and regenerative materials, the regeneration of natural ecosystems, and the utilization of renewable energy. The substitution of fossil-fuels with renewables both as an energy as well as a molecular carrier is fundamental in the chemical sector.

Narrow
use less material and energy

Close
use materials again

Slow
use products and components longer

Regenerate
use non-toxic material, renewable energy and regenerate natural ecosystems

Figure 1: Narrowing, Slowing, Closing and Regenerate Flows in the Butterfly diagram

This framework of narrow, slow, close and regenerate will be continually applied within the framework of WP4 activities and implementation. Table 2 provides a basic overview of how these four CE principles apply and relate to the BeBOP concept.

CE Principle		Strategy	Relevance and applicability for BeBOP
	Narrow	Use less material and energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Intensity of the process (esp. SOEC energy demand) • Resource efficiency (biomass conversion efficiency, MeOH yield) • Feedstock Flexibility
	Slow	Use products and components for longer time	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintenance and repair potentials of industrial components • Sensoring, Digital Twin and process monitoring
	Close	Material reuse	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potentials for Industrial Symbiosis (related to heat reutilization, waste stream valorisation and biomass use) • Recyclability of industrial components
	Regenerate	Use of non-toxic material energy and regenerate natural ecosystems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Renewable energy use • Biomass inflows from post use or waste sources (cascading) • Adaptability of the process to intermittent renewable energy supply • Water use and reutilization

Table 2: CEPs and their relevance for BeBOP

3. Goal of the Circularity Assessment and the Circularity Workshops

3.1. Objectives

Within the implementation of WP4, a total of six Circularity Workshops are organized with participants from the consortium, the Advisory Board and the Stakeholder Network. The goal of the Circularity Assessment conducted within these Workshops is to **identify the most relevant levers for improving the circularity of a scaled-up Methanol production plant based on the BeBOP process**. The intent is to identify, as early as the design phase and using the pilot plant as a reference, the most critical variables to maximize the process's circularity.

Figure 2 shows a simplified Diagram of the input and output flows of a scaled-up 100MW BeBOP process with clean wood, with rough estimations for the most relevant flows.³

Figure 2: Input-Output Diagram of the scaled-up BeBOP process

³ See also Syngas Electrolysis Scenario from: Rajaei et al., "Techno-Economic Evaluation of Biomass-to-Methanol Production via Circulating Fluidized Bed Gasifier and Solid Oxide Electrolysis Cells."

3.2. Life Cycle coverage and BeBOP alignment

To achieve the defined goal, ECODESIGN has planned the circularity workshops, aligned with the scaled-up BeBOP value chain, from the feedstock selection up to the product use (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Life Cycle Stages of the BeBOP process

The following is a short, simplified description of the defined Life Cycle Stages and their relation to circularity:

- Feedstock selection:** The process begins with the selection of a feedstock for the gasification. In BeBOP, five different feedstocks were predefined, with the process viability initially demonstrated using clean wood. Additional feedstocks to be tested include Miscanthus, willow and poplar from polluted soil, post-use wood, and straw pellets. From a circularity perspective, analysing the viability of secondary resources and cascade use is extremely relevant as their use lessens the general strain on biogenic resources and minimizes usage competition. Furthermore, the proximity or even co-location with feedstock sources (Industrial Symbiosis) is important to analyse as the transport of feedstocks is expected to be a significant burden overall, simply due to the quantity needed for a scaled-up process.
- Feedstock pre-treatment:** Before being fed to the gasifier, feedstocks need to be sized (e.g., pelletised) and dried. From a circularity perspective, this stage involves a considerable amount of heat for drying, which could potentially be covered by waste heat from the production process.
- Gasification, Gas Cooling and Cleaning:** The selected feedstocks are processed in a Bubbling Fluidized Bed (BFB) Gasifier at 700-970°C to produce syngas. This syngas is then cooled and cleaned of tars and ashes, as the downstream SOECs require high-purity syngas. From a circularity perspective, key points of interest include heat recovery potentials, the gasifier's flexibility in handling various feedstocks, its downstream effects, and overall impacts on the gasifier's service life.
- SOEC/SOFC:** The syngas is fed into Solid Oxide Electrolysis Cells (SOECs), which add hydrogen to achieve an optimal syngas composition for the methanol synthesis. SOECs operate between 600–800°C and account for the majority of the overall electricity demand. The process also produces oxygen as a by-product, which is fed back to the gasifier to support gasification. The SOECs can also operate in reverse as Solid Oxide Fuel Cells (SOFCs), producing electricity from syngas when electricity prices and demand are particularly high. Circularity considerations include the type of electricity source used, influences on SOEC durability and performance, and the recoverability of valuable materials within SOEC cells.
- Syngas Compression and Methanol Synthesis:** The optimally composed syngas is then processed into methanol in a 3D-printed reactor specifically designed within the project. 3D printing allows for more complex reactor geometries than conventional methods, which should translate into better heat transfer and higher process yields. The

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syngas is processed in continuous loops, where only a portion is converted to methanol per loop. The process should also allow the dynamic operation between partial and full loads (25-100%). Important circularity topics to consider include heat reutilization from the exothermic synthesis, catalyst management and influences on service life, reactor durability and recyclability.

- **Product Use:** Methanol is a basic chemical used as a precursor for a wide range of applications in the chemical industry. It is also increasingly used as a final product for fuel or energy storage. From a circularity and sustainability perspectives, it is important to consider that, depending on the case of use, the inherent carbon is either stored (at least temporarily) or released as CO₂ when used as fuel.

4. Methodology of the Circularity Assessment

4.1. Identifying relevant standards and frameworks

As previously mentioned, compared to Life Cycle Assessment, measuring circularity and applying CE Principles is far less standardised in terms of the existing methodologies and indicators. Circularity indicators can be found in various contexts, such as sustainability reporting standards, environmental assessment tools, and voluntary company assessment frameworks.

This chapter preselected different frameworks and analysed how they measure circularity. The frameworks investigated include (see complete references in the list of sources):

- Circulytics, EllenMacArthur Foundation
- Circular Transition Indicators, World Business Council for Sustainable Development
- Material Circularity Indicator, Ellen MacArthur Foundation
- European Sustainability Reporting Standards
- ISO 59020. 2024: Circular Economy – Measuring and assessing circularity performance
- Global Reporting Initiative

The following Table 3 provides an overview of their purpose, applicability, and structure, while Table 4 lists related indicators and correlates them with the CE principles of narrow, slow, close, and regenerate.

Within sustainability reporting standards (such as the European Sustainability Reporting Standards -ESRS- and the Global Reporting Initiative Standards – GRI standards-) circularity metrics are included as a part of the overall sustainability metrics. These standards mainly cover the principle of “*narrowing*” and “*closing*” by focusing on the resource in and outflows within the technical cycle. The focus is on the source of materials used and the outflows of materials. The GRI standards additionally takes into consideration the energy requirements of products in the use phase and renewable energy consumption.

On the other hand, frameworks with a specific CE focus are generally voluntary self-assessments such as Circulytics, Material Circularity Indicator (MCI), Circular Transition Indicators (CTI), and International Standardisation Organisation (ISO), and offer a more in-depth analysis of the circularity paradigm. Table 4 to follow shows that these metrics also extensively cover the “*inner circles*” related to slowing by measuring product lifetime, product utility, product design, and inner loops like reuse, repair, and remanufacturing. Furthermore, the biological cycle is covered more comprehensively by measuring renewable energy flows and regenerative materials.

Framework	Organisation	Level of application	Industry specific / generic	Purpose	Version	CE-indicator related parts of the framework
Circulytics	Ellen MacArthur Foundation	Companies	Generic	Voluntary self-assessment	Last version 2022, discontinued	6. Products and Materials 9. Water 10. Energy
Circular Transition Indicators (CTI)	World Business Council of Sustainable Development	mainly companies (but also production lines, products)	Generic indicators, but sector specific guidance available	Standardised, quantitative, voluntary self-assessment for reporting and transformation	Version 4, 2023	1. Close the loop 2. Optimize the loop 3. Value the Loop 4. Impact of the Loop
Material Circularity Indicator (MCI)	Ellen MacArthur Foundation	Products and materials	Generic (technical cycle only)	Voluntary product assessment	Adapted by thinkstep, Version 2023	All
European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS)	EU	Companies	Generic (future sector specific standards are being worked on)	Mandatory reporting assessment for large companies (+250 employees), future phase-in for SMEs	2023	E1 Climate Change E3 Water and marine resources E5 Resource use and Circular Economy
ISO 59020:2024	ISO	Mainly companies, but also applicable to regions or products	Generic	Guidance for organizations to assess circularity	Version 2024	Core Circularity Indicators (Annex A) A2 Resource inflows A3 Resource outflows A4 Energy A5 Water A6 Economic Additional Circularity Indicators (Annex B) B2 Resource inflows B3 Resource outflows B4 Energy B5 Water B6 Economic
Global Reporting Initiative (GRI)	Global Reporting Initiative	Companies	Generic, but sector specific standards in development for 40 priority sectors including chemicals	Measurement and report of ESG impacts	Version 2016 (301,302,303), Version 2020(306)	301 Materials 302 Energy 303 Water and Effluents 306 Waste

Table 3: Overview of CE-related Indicator Frameworks

Framework	List of indicators along CE principles			
	Narrow	Slow	Close	Regenerate
Circulytics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - % inflows from non-virgin material (6a) - % inflows from by products or waste streams (6a) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - % of products designed for long life, reuse, repair (6d) - % of products recirculated for reuse, remanufacturing (6f1) - average reuse cycles (6f2) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - % of production waste to landfill or incineration (6b) - % of products designed for disassembly, refurbishment, recycling or nutrient recirculation (6d) - % of products recirculated for upstream recycling or nutrient recirculation (6f1) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - % renewable and regeneratively produced inflows (6a) - % renewable and sustainably produced inflows (6a) - % of products of regeneratively grown materials (6d) - % product compliance with REACH and C2C Certification (6e)
Circular Transition Indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - % critical inflow (2) - % circular inflow (circular material productivity (revenue / total mass inflow) (1) - CTI product revenue (% circular flows * revenue) (3) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - actual lifetime (compared to industry average) in years or use cycles (2) - % recovery type (reuse, repair, remanufacture) (2) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - % circular outflow (1) - % material circularity (weighted average of circular Inflow and outflows) (1) - % recovery type recycling (2) - % recovery potential (2) - % actual recovery (2) - % water circularity (1) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - % renewable energy (1) - GHG impact (4) - Nature impact (4)
Material Circularity Indicator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - % input source (reuse / reman / recycled / virgin) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - product utility (lifetime OR use intensity compared to reference product) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - % output collection rate per destination (reuse / reman/ recycling/ compost / energy recovery / landfill) 	
European Sustainability Reporting Standards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - weight of inflows (materials, associated process materials, semimanufactured goods and parts) (E5-4) - weight and % of inflows sourced from by-products and wastes (E5-4) - anticipated CE risks and opportunities in € (E5-6) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - weight and % of resource outflow waste streams from production processes (E5-5) 	
ISO 59020:2024 (Core Circularity indicators)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - % reused content of an inflow (A2.2) - % recycled content of an inflow (A2.3) - % water from circular sources (A5.2) - material productivity (revenue per mass of linear inflows) (A6.2) - resource intensity index (economic growth vs. resource use) (A6.3) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - average material/product lifetime relative to industry average (A3.2) - % actual outflow that is reused (A3.3) - ratio of water reuse (A5.4) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - % actual outflow that is recycled (A3.4) - % water discharged in accordance with circularity principles (A5.3) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - % renewable content of an inflow (A2.3) - % actual outflow that is recirculated in biological cycle (A3.5) - % renewable energy consumed (A4.2)
ISO 59020: 2024 (Additional Circularity Indicators)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - energy intensity (energy use per given output) (B4.3) - water intensity (water use per given output) (B5.3) - net value added (value per unit negative economic factor costs) (B6.3) - value per mass (value per unit mass of resource) (B6.4) - resource productivity (ratio of GDP to DMC/RMC) (B6.5) - genuine process indicator (GDP after negative impacts) (B6.6) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> % reusability based on design (B3.2) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - % recyclability based on design (B3.3) - nutrient extraction from discharged water (B5.2) 	
GRI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - materials used by weight and volume (301-1) - recycled input materials used (301-2) - reclaimed products and their packaging materials (303-3) - energy intensity (energy per unit output) (302-3) - reduction of energy consumption due to conservation or efficiency measures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - reductions in energy requirements of products and services (302-5) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - % of waste diverted from disposal and sent to reuse, recycling or recovery processes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - renewable energy consumption (302-1)

Table 4: Indicators for Circularity along the CE principles

4.2. Understanding circularity challenges in BeBOP

While Circular Economy principles can theoretically be applied to all economic sectors involving material flows, it is important to understand the evolution of their application. A primary driver for the Circular Economy was the EU's introduction of the Circular Economy Action Plan in 2015, which regulated measures for specific product groups and sectors. Its first iteration included plastics, critical raw materials, and construction products, among others. Building on this Action Plan, regulations were continually expanded to include further product groups such as electronics, batteries, packaging, and textiles. Existing standards, frameworks, and indicators reflect these product categories.

Currently, to the knowledge of the authors, there is no specific guidance for circularity tailored to the chemistry sector or industrial equipment. Furthermore, the generic indicators best applicable to the BeBOP process (especially from ISO 59020:2024 and the Circular Transition Indicators) are only suitable for analysing established processes. They are not designed to analyse the circularity of an industrial process in its design phase, as is the aim here. However, even if the indicators cannot be calculated directly, they highlight variables that are important to consider early in the design phase.

4.3. Applied Methodology for the Circularity Assessment Workshops

Based on the considerations in the previous chapter, the following process is designed to analyse the levers for circularity of a scaled-up BeBOP process:

1. Select a specific segment of the value chain from the BeBOP process for further analysis within a workshop
2. Select and invite relevant stakeholders as workshop participants
3. Select relevant and applicable circularity indicators
4. Apply the CE principles of narrowing, slowing, closing and regenerating flows
5. Rate the importance of each CE principle
6. Define specific topics of interest for circularity
7. Define detailed discussion questions
8. Derive levers for circularity from the discussion

The following chapter describes how this methodology was applied in the BeBOP Circularity Workshops.

5. Specific Workshop Concepts

5.1. Covering the Life Cycle stages

The Circularity Workshops aim to cover the entire Life Cycle of the BeBOP value chain, with a different focus in each Workshop. When the Life Cycle stage overlaps with the Project scope (Gasification and Cleaning, SOEC/SOFC, and Syngas Compression & MeOH Synthesis), the involvement of internal stakeholders is paramount. For Life Cycle stages not extensively covered within BeBOP (Feedstock Selection, Feedstock Pre-treatment, and Product Use), prioritizing the involvement of external expertise and stakeholders was instead the key. This was facilitated by establishing a strategic Stakeholder Network in parallel.

Table 5 to follow provides an overview of all the Workshop topics selected and the main life cycle stages that were covered. It is to be noted that the workshop plan is to be considered as a work in progress and subject to change as WP4 progresses. There is also a plan to facilitate a seventh workshop as a joint event together with the H4C community⁴ in the beginning of 2026, aiming to be more broadly about the potentials of Industrial Symbiosis for a scaled-up BeBOP process.

⁴ <https://www.h4c-community.eu/>

Workshop Theme (potential discussion topics)	Life Cycle Stages covered					
	Feedstock Selection	Feedstock Pre-treatment	Gasification, Cooling and Cleaning	SOEC / SOFC	Compression and MeOH synthesis	Product Use
Gasification Cooling and Cleaning (Impacts of Impurities, Feedstock Flexibility of Gasifier, Impacts on Component Lifetimes, Waste streams, heat integration)						
SOEC performance and production flexibility (CRMs used, modularity of stack design, SOFC use cases, longevity of SOEC, Flexibility of the SOEC production)						
Biomass Feedstocks (Usage Competition, Availability, Quality, Energy Intensity of Pre-treatment, Waste streams as feedstock inputs)						
Syngas Compression and Methanol Synthesis (Dynamic Load vs efficiency, Ease of Catalyst replacement, Catalyst Circularity, Heat integration potentials)						
Process Integration (Circularity takeaways so far, Integration, Scale-up uncertainties, definition of circularity Indicators for BeBOP)						
Business Models and Market opportunities of bio and e-Methanol (Industrial Symbiosis potentials, potential Business Models, future use cases and market opportunities) --> link to Task 11.3 Final business cases and Models						

Table 5: Overview of Workshop topics, life cycle coverage and stakeholder involvement

5.2. Applying CE principles

As no circularity frameworks specifically applicable to the chemistry sector or industrial processes were identified, ECODESIGN developed its own methodology. The goal was to build upon the generic indicators identified in Chapter 3.1 and apply them to the BeBOP process. This was done :

- First, by defining goals that the built BeBOP infrastructure should fulfil;
- Secondly, by identifying related indicators (see Table 6).

A circular scaled-up BeBOP infrastructure		Related Circularity Indicators
 Narrow	.. runs as efficiently as possible.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy efficiency • Resource efficiency • Share of renewable Energy • Water reutilization rate • Heat reutilization rate • Share of regenerative inputs • Avoided fossil fuel use
 Narrow and Slow	.. is adaptable to variable feedstocks.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of possible feedstock inputs • Average utilization rate • Minimal viable utilization rate
 Slow	.. consists of easily maintainable, repairable and upgradable components.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modularity of Structure • Availability of spare parts • Ease of maintenance • Ease of repairability • Ease of Upgradeability • Share of standard parts • Share of standard connections
 Slow	.. anticipates failures and errors.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Average Uptime • Availability of repair and maintenance protocols • Detectability of wear and degradation • Robustness under non-optimal conditions
 Slow	.. remains operational as long as possible.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Average lifetime of key components vs. industry standard • Average lifetime of infrastructure
 Close and Regenerate	.. makes use of waste streams from other Industries and provides valuable outputs to other Industries (<i>Industrial Symbiosis</i>).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Average reutilization rate of process outputs • Share of waste stream feedstocks as inputs
 Regenerate	.. anticipates its end of life.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Share of recyclable materials from infrastructure • Complexity of disassembly to material level • Detachability of connections • Share of components returnable to manufacturer

Table 6: Circularity goals for the BeBOP infrastructure and related indicators

These indicators are both quantitative and qualitative. The idea is not to use them directly for assessment, but rather to apply them for prioritizing the CE principles that are important to optimize, based on the design knowledge of the BeBOP pilot plant.

During the first BeBOP Circularity Workshop about Gasification, hosted by project partner VTT at the Technical Research Center of Finland, an attempt was made to evaluate the importance of these goals before proceeding to a more detailed discussion. A set of seven handouts (one for each circularity goal) was prepared to assess the applicability and relevance of the indicators listed in Table 6 for the Life Cycle stage under investigation (handouts are included in the Annex). However, this evaluation and pre-prioritization proved to be difficult and too abstract in practice. In subsequent workshops the methodology was adapted. It proved to be more practical to go directly into the discussion questions.

However, a prioritization of areas of interest based on the CE principles was done beforehand. To better understand this approach, Table 7 summarizes the areas of interest for the workshop about SOECs.

	Importance		Areas of Interest
	Secondary	Primary	
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of Critical Raw Materials (CRMs) and their possible substitution • Resource efficiency of the production (CRMs per cell) • Resource efficiency of the operation modes (energy input / kg Hydrogen)
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SOEC system is a key part of the overall Balance of Plant (expected ~ 1/3 of the Capex) • Understanding influences on the service life of SOECs • Integrated SOEC value chain (stack design, production and installation) offers potential for circularity • Realization of inner loops such as repair, remanufacturing, reverse logistics and recycling
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential to recover CRMs • Potential use of waste streams – esp. waste heat and oxygen
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential to use renewable electricity to fulfil SOEC power demand (electricity costs ~ 1/3 of the overall costs) • Potential of SOFC use case to provide renewable energy in high demand scenarios

Table 7: Areas of Interest of SOECs and the relevance of CE principles

A previous techno-economic analysis of a process similar to the BeBOP-design⁵ has shown that SOECs are one of the most cost-relevant factors concerning the Balance of Plant. This is due to their high investment costs and a relatively frequent replacement rate (~5 years) compared to other industrial equipment, coupled with the significant electricity demand of their operation. From a circularity perspective, this translates into a high priority for "slowing" strategies aimed at prolonging SOEC service life. Furthermore, understanding the framework conditions under which SOECs can be operated with intermittent renewables is paramount, highlighting the primary importance of the "regenerate" principle.

As SOECs require a broad range of Critical Raw Materials (CRMs), it is also important to investigate how their use can be minimized or substituted (narrowing), as well as understanding the potential to recover them from used cells (closing). The process also produces outflows of waste heat and oxygen, which can potentially be reintegrated elsewhere.

⁵ Rajaei et al., "Techno-Economic Evaluation of Biomass-to-Methanol Production via Circulating Fluidized Bed Gasifier and Solid Oxide Electrolysis Cells."

5.3. Defining discussion questions

Continuing with the SOEC workshop example to showcase the methodology: the previous analysis shows that all circularity principles are at least partly relevant to address within a workshop. Based on this analysis, specific workshop discussion questions were defined for further investigation (Table 8).

Discussion questions	
	<p>Critical Raw Materials:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the expected availability and substitutability of the CRMs used in SOECs? • Are there promising material alternatives to reduce reliance on critical elements? <p>Influences on operational efficiency:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What operating conditions (temperature, pressure) are key to optimize SOEC efficiency while reducing energy demand? • Which operating conditions allow a long service life of the SOEC components?
	<p>Capex / Opex and components´ lifetime:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How does the SOEC design change if optimized for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Capex/Opex ◦ What is the most valuable component? ◦ The longest possible component lifetime? <p>SOEC Lifetime:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How long is a typical lifetime of a SOEC? Which factors influence it the most? • How do different operating conditions (e.g., variable load, intermittent operation) affect SOEC degradation? <p>Modular design:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do individual cells degrade homogeneously or heterogeneously? • What is the smallest module (cells, stacks, assembly) that can be replaced? <p>Maintenance / Repairability:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the most failure-prone components in a SOEC stack? • Can they be designed for easier replacement or refurbishment? How? • Can predictive maintenance or advanced monitoring improve SOEC´ s longevity? If yes, how?
	<p>Business Models:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is a closed-loop system for SOEC materials/components feasible e.g., secondary markets for refurbished cells or recycling of critical materials? • Electrochemical cell recycling (as for batteries) for SOECs? <p>Recycling:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the challenges in recovering and reusing key materials (e.g., YSZ, perovskite-based electrodes) from decommissioned stacks? • Are there alternative cell designs that could enhance recycling? <p>Use of resource streams:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is the SOEC system designed to allow oxygen use in the gasification unit? • Is the SOEC system designed to use waste heat from another unit? • How to improve the water cycle to supply the SOEC with ultra-pure water?
	<p>Influences of operational flexibility:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Should a location with direct/near access to renewable energy sources (e.g., wind, solar) be considered for the BeBOP plant? • Is it feasible to adapt the processes to a variable input of renewable energy sources (e.g. solar or wind)? If yes, how would that influence the process efficiency? • If SOECs are powered by intermittent renewable supply, is it needed /preferable to use a hydrogen buffer storage or an electrical battery storage? • What is the potential of the SOFC use case to provide renewable energy in high demand scenarios? What are the repercussions in the downstream process? <p>SOFC mode:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the (best) conditions to switch to SOFC mode? • How flexible is the switching to the SOFC mode? • What are the impacts on the other processes (e.g., gasification and MeOH synthesis)?

Table 8: Discussion questions along CE principles for the workshop about SOECs

Outlook

At the time of writing of this report, the Workshops are currently being organised and held. The findings will be published in Deliverable 4.2. titled "*Validated strategies for ensuring sustainable circularity plans*", scheduled for publication in March 2026.

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Annex (Handouts from VTT's Workshop)

A Circular Gasification Infrastructure..

1. .. runs as efficiently as possible.

Example: Reduction of energy demand

Source: TU Wien / Ergo

Evaluate the relevance for BeBOP

	not relevant	relevant
Energy efficiency	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Resource efficiency	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Share of renewable energy	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Water reutilization rate	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Heat reutilization rate	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Share of renewable inputs	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Avoided fossil fuel use	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

relevant? turn page

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A Circular Gasification Infrastructure..

1. .. runs as efficiently as possible.

Discussion

- What are the most important factors that influence the efficiency of the process?
 - Feedstock quality and composition
 - Utilization rate
 - Moisture content
 - Plant condition
 - Other
- Which performance feedback mechanisms could be incorporated to monitor efficiency?
- Which water reutilization rates are achievable and by which means?
- What are possible internal heat reutilization potentials of the process?

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A Circular Gasification Infrastructure..

2. .. is adaptable to changing conditions.

Example: Flexible engines

Source: Toyota/Lexus

Source: MWM.com

Evaluate the relevance for BeBOP

	not relevant	relevant
Number of possible feedstock inputs	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
High average utilization rate	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Minimal viable utilization rate	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

relevant? turn page

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A Circular Gasification Infrastructure..

2. .. is adaptable to changing circumstances.

Discussion

- How adaptable can the plant be designed to process different feedstocks?
- What are the tradeoffs of feedstock flexibility for the plant design and operation?
- Can different „biomass families“ with similar characteristics be defined that are compatible with the gasification infrastructure?
- How do different biomass families perform related to:
 - Quantity (high vs. low availability)
 - Usage Competition (unrivaled vs. plenty alternative use cases)
 - Seasonality (highly seasonal vs. consistent)
 - Distribution and transport (highly concentrated vs. highly distributed)
 - Pretreatment intensity (unchanged vs. high pretreatment effort)

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A Circular Gasification Infrastructure..

3. .. consists of easily maintainable, repairable and upgradable components.

Example: Modular design for Remanufacturing

Evaluate the relevance for BeBOP

	not relevant	relevant
Modularity of structure	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Availability of spare parts	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Ease of Maintenance	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Ease of Repairability	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Ease of Upgradability	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Share of standard parts	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Share of standard connections	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

relevant? turn page

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A Circular Gasification Infrastructure..

3. .. consists of easily maintainable, repairable and upgradable components.

Discussion

- How modular can the infrastructure be designed, so that
 - high value components,
 - parts with different functions and
 - different lifetimes are separately accessible and exchangeable?
- What are the most commonly needed spare parts? Are these easily available and for which would it make sense to have them available on-site?
- Are there ways these components are designed in a way to ease repair and maintenance?
- Are there specific components where it makes sense to design them to be upgradable? (e.g. due to expected efficiency gains during the long plant lifetime)
- Are the connections between components standardized and easily detachable?

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A Circular Gasification Infrastructure..

4. .. anticipates failures and errors.

Example: Automatic cleaning systems for various industrial boilers

Evaluate the relevance for BeBOP

	not relevant	relevant
Average Uptime	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Availability of repair and maintenance protocols	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Detectability of wear and degradation	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

relevant? turn page

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A Circular Gasification Infrastructure..

4. .. anticipates failures and errors.

Discussion

- How easily are wear and degradations detectable? Can wear and degradations be predicted? (e.g. via performance monitoring, sensors, modeling etc)
- What are the potential consequences of a gasifier shutdown and how can these be minimized? What options to minimize downtime do exist? (e.g. monitoring, robotic maintenance)
- How can repair and maintenance protocols contribute to a smooth operation?

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A Circular Gasification Infrastructure..

5. .. remains operational as long as possible.

Example: Life extension for electric infrastructure

Evaluate the relevance for BeBOP

Average lifetime of key components vs. industry standard not relevant relevant

Average lifetime of infrastructure

Robustness under non-optimal conditions

relevant? turn page

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A Circular Gasification Infrastructure..

5. .. remains operational as long as possible.

Discussion

- What are the most important influences on the life time of components (esp. high-value and process critical components)?
 - Feedstock quality
 - Impurities
 - Moisture
 - Load Variability
 - Other
- Which specific components are mostly affected by these influences?
- How do design choices influence the lifetime of these components?
- What is the minimum viable utilization rate?
- Are there tradeoffs of a high load variability and plant life time?

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A Circular Gasification Infrastructure..

6. .. makes use of waste streams from other industries, provides valuable outputs to other industries.

Example: Industrial symbiosis network

Evaluate the relevance for BeBOP

Average reutilization rate of process outputs not relevant relevant

Share of waste stream feedstocks (from all inputs)

relevant? turn page

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A Circular Gasification Infrastructure..

6. .. makes use of waste streams from other industries, provides valuable outputs to other industries.

Discussion

- Which would be potentially important feedstock inputs for a scaled-up gasification plant in Finland?
- What is the typical amount and composition of the waste streams from the gasification plant (e.g. ashes, tar, chars) in relation to the quantity of the input?
- What would be possible revalorization routes for these waste streams?
- What is the heat recuperation potential of the gasification plant?
- What would be an optimal location and size of the plant, considering the rationality to feedstocks, the potential for heat recovery, the valorization routes of the waste streams

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A Circular Gasification Infrastructure..

7. ... considers its end of life.

Example: Closed loop for wind rotor blade recycling

Evaluate the relevance for BeBOP

	not relevant	relevant
Share of recyclable materials from infrastructure	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Complexity of disassembly to material level	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Detachability of connections	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Share of components that are returnable to manufacturer	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

relevant? turn page

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A Circular Gasification Infrastructure..

7. ... considers its end of life.

Discussion

- Are individual components / modules / skids returnable to the producer enabling high-value loops?
- How complex is the disassembly process (esp. related to parts that are often exchanged)?
- How diverse are the materials used?
- Are different materials easily separable?
- Are materials recyclable at their end of life?
- Is there a concept for "mining materials from the gasification plant" at its end of life, to feed the materials into other value chains?

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